

Welcome to our March cybersphere insights edition!

As [COcyber](#) moves forward, we are excited to share some key developments shaping our mission. This second edition unveils an opportunity to join our [AI Cybersecurity Deephack](#) – a challenge to fight phishing threats with AI-driven solutions, introduces [our first onboarded ambassadors](#) and highlights [insights from our collaboration needs assessment report](#).

AI Cybersecurity Deephack – Can AI Stop the Next Big Phishing Attack?

 24 – 26 April | Online

Phishing attacks are becoming increasingly sophisticated— will **Artificial Intelligence** stay ahead?

COcyber is launching the [AI Cybersecurity Deephack](#) to address this urgent challenge, inviting participants to build AI-driven solutions using #NLP, anomaly detection, and real-time threat intelligence that stop phishing attacks before they strike.

The banner features a woman's face in the background with digital code overlaid. The COcyber logo is in the top right. The main text reads 'AI cybersecurity deephack' with a large stylized 'C' logo. Below it, it says 'Advancing European defence capabilities'. A blue button contains the text 'April 24–26, 2025 Online [zoom]'. At the bottom, there are logos for 'Funded by the European Union', 'ECCC EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY COMPETENCE CENTRE', 'IN COLLABORATION WITH EIT Digital', and 'POWERED BY ULTRAHACK'.

This is an opportunity for **start-ups, SMEs and corporates, government and law enforcement tech teams, cybersecurity professionals, and university students** working on cybersecurity-related deep tech.

🏆 Mentorship, acceleration support, and visibility within the cybersecurity ecosystem for the winning teams.

➔ [Apply now to take part in the challenge!](#)

COcyber Ambassadors – Strengthening Cybersecurity Collaboration

We are proud to welcome **six distinguished cybersecurity professionals** as the first cohort of #COcyberAmbassadors. Their expertise spans AI-driven security, cyber policy, digital forensics, and cyber intelligence, bringing a wealth of experience in tackling cybersecurity challenges.

Throughout their six-month involvement, they help **bridge gaps between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities**, contribute to policy discussions, and support COcyber’s outreach and impact.

The graphic displays six COcyber Ambassadors for Batch 1. Each ambassador is represented by a circular portrait, their name, and their affiliation. The central text reads "COcyber AMBASSADORS #BATCH1". Logos for the European Union and ECCC are also present.

Name	Affiliation
Eduvigis Ortiz	Women4Cyber Spain
Antonio Grasso	Digital Business Innovation Italy
Stella Tsitsoula	RED Communications Greece
Madhusanka Liyanage	University College Dublin Ireland
Selene Giupponi	Resecurity Inc Italy
Nizar Touleimat	CEA-List France

Meet Our Ambassadors and learn more about their role [HERE](#)

- ▶ [Eduvigis Ortiz](#): Founder and President of [Women4Cyber Spain \(W4C Spain\)](#).
- ▶ [Nizar Touleimat](#): Director of the Research and Innovation program at [CEA-List Institute](#).
- ▶ [Stella Tsitsoula](#): Founder [Hellenic Cybersecurity Institute](#)
- ▶ [Madhusanka Liyanage](#): Associate Professor at [University College Dublin](#).
- ▶ [Antonio Grasso](#): Founder and CEO of [Digital Business Innovation Srl - dbi.srl Srl](#).
- ▶ [Selene Giupponi](#): Managing Director for Europe at [Resecurity](#).

Bridging Gaps – COcyber Needs Assessment Report

📖 COcyber's [Bridging Gaps: A Raw Needs Assessment Report for Enhanced Collaboration Between Civilian and Defence Cybersecurity Spheres](#) – led by [Université libre de Bruxelles / Solvay Brussels School of Economics and Management](#) – explores the challenges, opportunities, and solutions for fostering stronger cybersecurity partnerships across Europe.

To build a comprehensive understanding, the study used a participatory approach, combining a quantitative survey, qualitative focus group discussions, and consultations with key stakeholders – including representatives from European institutions, national defence ministries, cybersecurity agencies, industry players, and research institutions.

 Are you a cybersecurity professional? Your insights matter! The survey behind this report is still open.

 Fill in the survey [HERE](#)

What's Next?

COcyber remains committed to building a stronger, more interconnected European cybersecurity landscape. With our ambassadors onboard, our ongoing research, community engagement efforts and events, we are taking concrete steps toward fostering meaningful collaboration.

Stay connected for more updates, and join us to contribute your expertise in driving innovation and collaboration to enhance Europe's cybersecurity resilience!

Don't miss any opportunities, follow us on [Linkedin](#) and [Bluesky](#) and register now via cocyber.eu!

 For any collaboration query, you can also reach out to us directly at contact@cocyber.eu

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